

EXPRESSIVENESS OF MUSIC IN TELEVISION SHOWS

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Abstract: The power of music in television shows to make the imagination more vivid in the minds of the viewers and to get an impression of characters and themes in telenovelas, teleplays, movies, and TV shows, from plots to small episodes, were discussed.

Key words: telenovela, teleplay, movie, TV show, music, television, TV movie, TV program, concert, plot,

Аннотация: Обсуждалась способность музыки в телешоу оживлять воображение зрителей и формировать представление о персонажах и темах теленовелл, телеспектаклей, фильмов и телешоу, от сюжетов до небольших эпизодов.

Ключевые слова: теленовелла, телеспектакль, кино, телешоу, музыка, телевидение, телефильм, телепрограмма, концерт, сюжет,

Аннотация: Мусиқа телевидения дастурларидаги намойишларда телетомошабинлар онггида тасаввурни аниқроқ воқеилашишидаги кучи ва теленовеелла, телеспектакл, кино, телекўрсатувлардаги образлар ва мавзу, сюжетлардан тортиб кичик эпизодларгача таассурот олиш масаласида фикр юритилган.

Калит сўзлар: теленовеелла, телеспектакл, кино, телекўрсатув, мусиқа, телевидения, телефильм, теледастур, концерт, сюжет,

Introduction. Music for television refers to works taken from ready-made musical compositions or musical phonograms recorded for special television programs, telefilms, teleplays, and selected works for video series instead of original music. In this regard, the biggest and most responsible task is to achieve maximum organic methodical integrity when including the work of different authors or one composer in the program. Sometimes it is possible to refer to arrangements of folk, popular, pop songs available for compilation.

That is, music can be original and compilation on television. In telefilms (or teleplays), music becomes an integral part of its overall image. Including both dramaturgy and stylistic aspects, the music helps to clarify the compositional structure of the work, the mood in the frame, plot lines and genre symbols. It is able to reveal the social and national environment of the movement, to develop the historical time, period, space and time dimensions of the television work, as well as the unique aspects of the author.

Methods. Music has become popular on TV as an example of staged concert programs. Based on their scenario plan and the director's interpretation, performances by orchestras, choirs, and soloists are supplemented with visual material (films and photographs). For such staged concert performances, advanced artists are attracted to read the text or conduct the concert on television, performing episodes between concert numbers. On television, the staged-concert, based on the script, usually appears in two forms, depending on the topic of the program:

- TV programs based on symphonic, camera, song programs
- are shows dedicated to the creativity of representatives of musical culture or musical groups creating in all musical genres.
- The appearance of musical entertainment on television is mainly limited to three genres. Here are the following TV shows:
 - musical show based on the plot, staged based on the original script, the director will set the numbers, determine their television solution, the director will work directly with the composer, ballet master, performers and teams.
 - Shows with no obligation to stage numbers or reinterpret them

- Live broadcasts from the concert hall, without using additional television plots.

In turn, musical shows can be divided into 4 types based on genre:

- staged (concert films),

- staged - concerts (concerts to be held in our country on the occasion of the holiday),

- concert (television concerts consisting of works of various singers, performers and groups)

- broadcasted concerts (samples recorded and broadcast directly from the concert hall, hall, palace) are included.

Results. Music manifests itself harmoniously to all the functions of mass media, including television, performed in society. In particular, it performs the task of providing information to the audience (it introduces the audience to all the phenomena, realities in the music culture and art and the informative musical information related to them). The cultural, educational and propaganda mission is reflected in the presentation of national heritage, classical and classic works through television shows and concerts. Integrative (that is, regardless of nationality, religion, sect, age) the unifying factor defines itself as an important aspect of art forms. There aren't many, if not a few, musical shows that do an educational job. However, there are musical broadcasts and shows that have a pedagogical (that is, directing and guiding) task for the audience. In most cases, all musical shows have a recreational function (to provide the audience with entertainment, to focus on collecting the energy spent during the day).

As you know, the scope of the show can be limited to the musical text or provide additional information: oral commentary, interview, reportage, introduction. This broad category of television programs includes opera and ballet performances, concerts, broadcasts recorded from theaters and concert halls or television studios, and music-publicist programs.

Discussion. It should be noted that the musical work featured in such shows serves the primary purpose of showing music. In some programs, music is used to support visual images, and in such programs, music becomes the main theme, the main subject, and the basis for reasoning.

The following software can also be classified according to installation, structure, and broadcast conditions. In particular, musical programs classified on the basis of montage - staged and broadcast, simple and complex compositions according to the structure, pre-recorded or broadcast live.

These types can also affect the interpretation of musical works in a certain sense.

Nowadays, it is no secret to anyone that musical works occupy a strong place on television for their philharmonic purpose. It is known that the new performance environment of a musical work changes more and more. Broadcasting of the works created for the live concert process in its television interpretation is able to turn it into a new "music-television work".

The television screen has expanded the possibilities of reception and perception of music. In particular, the possibility of 100 million spectators watching a single concert at the same time indicates its promotion and spiritual-educational tasks.

As you know, most of the programs on television are musical. In every corner of the world, TV viewers have the opportunity to get to know and enjoy the brightest masterpieces of world music, opera and ballet performances, contests and festivals, national art of different peoples. Through television, composers, conductors and performers give interesting lectures in front of millions of listeners.

But bringing a musical program to the screen is a painstaking process. In addition to performers, more than 120 employees participate in the creation of a single musical show. These are directors, cameramen, editors and artists, sound directors and video engineers, lighting designers, editors and representatives of other fields. .

Among the musical programs - broadcasting of Independence, Navruz joyous holidays, concerts broadcast from concert palaces, musical programs filmed in a television studio, contests, music broadcasts, etc. Among them, television film-concerts recorded in nature (for example, pop or folklore programs, etc.). Sometimes we listen to music broadcasts and programs from other countries without translation on television, the common language of music unites thousands of people in front of the TV screen.

The telescreen not only erases space and time boundaries, but also contributes to the process of his perception. Ekran Turgun Alimatov, Halima Nasirova, Tavakll Kadyrov, Botir Zakirov, Munojat Ylchieva, Muyassar Razzakova and other such great singers and performers reveal the miracle of art to TV viewers.

In most cases, music is shown on the TV screen together with dance, visual arts, sharia and theater. Color, sound, word unit create a new interpretation and meaning in musical programs. Symbols of other types of art in films and shows help to understand and perceive music more deeply, to feel its mood. The visual world of music is displayed on the screen, and in exchange for the unity of the screen element of television - the sound and image line, the unity desired by many creators is realized. Even opera and ballet are reborn in front of the screen. Many composers create music for special teleopera and teleballet.

The programs and shows of the second group are far from the musical background and play behind the scenes, performing one or another task. Although the genres of television have not been fully studied, but depending on the task performed and the place occupied in the program, there is a musical introduction (initial and final), a clip (advertising or presenting the product of the TV channel). The music used in this type of show becomes another component of the whole unit

Conclusion. Music on television should help the audience understand all the different genres of television. In terms of music promotion, television tries to promote itself on the basis of sorting and selecting examples of national and world music art, as well as introducing the activities and creative products of advanced modern artists, providing information about various composers, musical directions and performance schools, and introducing them to everyone. is committed to understanding and researching the main forms of the factors of musical life in our country and abroad in a suitable form. Music on television is primarily distinguished by its uniqueness, and while embodying the nature of the small screen, it is finally close to the role of film music. In this regard, we found it necessary to make a special stop on the use of music in telefilms. This is caused by objective factors, such as the commonality of aesthetic nature between these types of artistic creations, such as cinema and television.

In this respect, in a certain sense, one can draw an equal sign between the creation of music for film and TV films. Television's use of musical elements in artistic forms has its clear appearance from the small screen element, the expressive basis of the artistic braze taken as a serial, the wide use of large shots, the close-up camera method of reception, etc. In Uzbek television series, a special place is allocated to the leitmotif of artistic and expressive importance. The leitmotif system appears in opera, then in cinematography, and then in a new interpretation on television. In large television series, the musical leitmotif performs a double task: to reveal the main idea and to integrate, that is, at the level of form, to unite all the series to the level of artistic integrity.

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